

IN VITRO PLANT REGENERATION OF TOBACCO (*Nicotiana* sp.) USING LEAF EXPLANT

A C Roy, A K Azad¹, M Hasanuzzaman¹, *M Arifuzzaman² and M A Tayeb³

Present address

¹Associate Professor
²Assistant Professor
Dept. of Genetics and
Plant Breeding, HSTU
Dinajpur ³FMO, Bayer
Crop Sci. Bangladesh

Correspondence

*arif_gpb@yahoo.com

Accepted: 20 July 2010

Abstract

The experiment was carried out during November 2008 to April 2009, in the Tissue Culture Laboratory of the Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Dinajpur. Five genotypes of tobacco (*Nicotiana* sp.) were used for observing their callus induction and subsequent plantlet regeneration ability by using leaf discs as explant. Leaf discs of five genotypes were cultured on hormone free MS medium and MS medium with four different combinations of kinetin and BAP (6-Benzyl Amino Purine) with a constant concentration of IAA (Indole Acetic Acid) for callus induction and shoot regeneration. A wide range of variation was observed by the explants and genotypes in different media. In case of callus induction, average callusing was highest in Virginia (72.33%) followed by CC Bengal (64.33%), Jati (55.33%), Motihari (47.67%) and Kobi (44.00%). Callusing was highest (77.00%) in T₄ (MS + 2 mg/liter BAP + 0.5 mg/liter IAA) and no callusing was observed in T₁ (hormone free MS medium). Among the tested genotypes, the remarkable regeneration were found in Virginia (100%) at treatment T₂ (MS + 2 mg/liter kinetin + 0.5 mg/liter IAA) and T₄ (MS + 2 mg/liter BAP + 0.5 mg/liter IAA) treatments. All the genotypes showed the satisfactory callusing or regeneration etc. under T₂ treatment. For root induction, three treatments were used but maximum result (90%) was obtained in Virginia under T₁ and T₃ (hormone free MS medium) treatment and T₃ treatment showed the superior results against all the genotypes. The survival rate of the plantlets in pot was maximum (80% both) in Virginia and CC Bengal. Among the five genotypes, it was revealed that Virginia showed the best performance for almost all the parameters, callus induction, shoot regeneration and root formation potentiality considered in the study followed by CC Bengal, Jati, Motihari and Kobi.

Key words: *In vitro* regeneration, leaf explant, Tobacco

Introduction

Tobacco is a major cash crop of tropical countries and has a considerable economic significance to Bangladesh. There are many species of tobacco, which are encompassed by the genus of herb *Nicotiana*. Its leaf is the useful part of the plant and the leaf area ranges about 1.0 to 1.5 square feet. A single plant with 18 leaves may produce more than 25 square feet of leaf (Alam *et al.*, 1989). Tobacco has a prestigious and significant position in Bangladesh in terms of economy where about 2-3 million people are employed for its production, processing and marketing. In Bangladesh, tobacco occupies the fourth position after jute, sugarcane and tea. The acreage and production of tobacco in Bangladesh during 2005-2006 fiscal years were 78385 tons and 42710 tons respectively (BBS, 2006). Out of 15-17 tobacco growing districts, Rangpur tops the list (50% of the total production) both in acreage and production followed by Kustia. There are few important tobacco varieties in Bangladesh viz. Virginia, Jati, Motihari, CC Bengal, Kobi etc. Motihari belongs to *Nicotiana rustica* and the others belong to *Nicotiana tabacum*. Virginia is a recognized cigarette variety while others are used for Hokka, Biri and Zarda purposes.

As tobacco has a significant contribution in our economy that is why, more and more attention should

be given for improving its quality and higher production. Conventional breeding method alone is insufficient to satisfy the goal as it demands more land, labour and capital. It also takes a long time to develop a potential variety. So, in this context, plant tissue culture technique could be a better alternative to design our target plant. There is no doubt that *in vitro* regeneration in tobacco has the great potentiality for improving tobacco. Furthermore, Tobacco callus culture used as a propagating medium for cucumber mosaic virus (Afifi *et al.* 2007).

Although tissue culture techniques in tobacco have been successful from a long period ago (Blakeslec *et al.*, 1992), but in Bangladesh its application is limited. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to study the *in vitro* regeneration performance of five varieties of cultivated *Nicotiana* species and also observed the callus induction, shoot regeneration and root formation potentiality of five cultivars of tobacco using leaf disc.

Materials and Methods

The experimental material used in the present investigation is the seed of five tobacco varieties viz. Virginia, CC Bengal, Jati, Motihari and Kobi. The seed materials of five investigated tobacco varieties were obtained from the local dealer, seed grower of Rangpur Sadar Upazila, Rangpur. The whole experiment has

been conducted in the Tissue Culture Laboratory of the Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Dinajpur. The duration of the experiment was November, 2008 to April, 2009.

All the instruments relevant to *in vitro* culture, glassware, and culture media were properly sterilized using different sterilizing agents. Sterilized seeds were placed on half strength MS medium (Murashige and Skoog, 1962) for seed germination in vial. In each vial, 15-20 seeds were inoculated. The culture was then incubated in incubation room till the germination of seeds. The age of the seedlings used for explants were 18 days. Comparatively large and mature leaves were separated from the seedlings. The separated leaf was then cut into many small segments with the help of sterile scalped and forceps and placed upright with cut ends embedded in the sterile culture medium for callus induction. It is also mentioned here that different concentrations and combinations of growth regulators like BAP (1 and 2 mg /liter), kinetin (1 and 2 mg /liter), and a fixed concentration of IAA (0.5 mg/liter) were used with MS medium for callus induction and direct regeneration from callus. In each vial, four leaf segments were placed. The culture vial containing explants were placed under florescent light in a room with controlled temperature using 16 hours photoperiod. The vials were checked daily to note the response and the development of contamination. Callus was initiated nine days after inoculation and after four weeks, inoculated explants were transferred on the fresh medium.

The sub culturing media in the present investigation were MS containing different combinations and concentrations of kinetin and IAA. Repeated subcultures were done at an interval of 15 days and incubated under the same temperature as mentioned previously for maintenance of calli and organogenesis. The sub cultured calli continued to proliferate and differentiated into shoots. When these shoots grew about 2-3 cm in length, they were rescued aseptically from the cultured vials and were separated from each

other and again cultured on vials with freshly prepared root induction medium containing full and half without or with 0.5mg /liter. When the plantlets became 5-8 cm in height with sufficient root system, they were taken out from the vials. The plantlets were then transplanted to pot containing potting mixture mentioned above. Immediately after transplantation, the plants along with the pots were covered with moist polythene bag to prevent desiccation. To reduce sudden shock, the pots were kept in a growth room for 7-15 days under controlled environments. The interior of the polythene bags was sprayed with distilled water at every 24 hrs to maintain high humidity around the plantlets. At the same time, plantlets were also nourished with Hoagland's solution. Finally, after 15-20 days they were transferred to the field condition. The data for the parameters under present study were statistically analyzed wherever applicable. The Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) compared the analysis of variance for different parameters.

Results and Discussion

In this piece of work, various parameters such as callus induction, shoot regeneration and root formation potentiality were made on induction of calli and their regeneration ability in different genotypes of *Nicotiana* species.

Callus induction

Leaf discs from 18 days old seedlings of five *Nicotiana* genotypes were cultured on MS medium supplemented with different combinations and concentrations of phytohormones for callus induction. Cultured leaf discs on the callus induction medium showed change from regular to irregular shape within four days of incubation. The initial response of leaf explants was the gradual expansion of the cut ends of the leaf segments. Callus was initiated following swelling midrib and then from other cut ends. In the culture, visible callus appeared eight days after inoculation and was completed within 32 days. Color of the callus also gives a gradual change from initial

Table 1. Analysis of variance for callus induction in Tobacco (*Nicotiana* sp.)

Sources of variation	Degrees of freedom (df)	Mean Square (MS)		
		Total no. of explants showing callus	% callus induction	Days required for callus initiation
Variety	4	614.980**	15374.500**	253.567**
Treatment	4	82.113**	2052.833**	3.033**
Variety x treatment	16	26.705*	667.625*	1.350*
Error	50	0.667	16.667	0.333
Total	74	-	-	-
Co-efficient of variation (%)	-	7.20%	7.20%	7.87%

** Indicates significant at 1% level of probability and * indicates significant at 5% level of probability

Table 2. Performance of different treatment for callus induction of five varieties of *Nicotiana* species

Treatments	Variety	No. of callus induction	% callus induction	Days required for callus initiation	Colour of callus	Nature of callus	Abundance of callus
T ₁ (Hormone free)	Virginia	0.000 l	0.000 l	0.000 f	-	-	-
	CC Bengal	0.000 l	0.000 l	0.000 f	-	-	-
	Jati	0.000 l	0.000 l	0.000 f	-	-	-
	Motihari	0.000 l	0.000 l	0.000 f	-	-	-
	Kobi	0.000 l	0.000 l	0.000 f	-	-	-
T ₂ (2 mg/liter kinetin)	Virginia	18.67 ab	93.33 ab	8.333 de	Creamy	Compact	Plenty
	CC Bengal	16.00 c-e	80.00 c-e	9.333 b-d	Creamy	Compact	Moderate
	Jati	14.67 e-g	73.33 e-g	9.000 b-e	Yellow	Friable	Moderate
	Motihari	15.67 d-f	78.33 d-f	8.000 e	Creamy	Compact	Moderate
	Kobi	7.333 jk	36.67 jk	9.333 b-d	Yellow	Loose	Poor
T ₃ (1 mg/liter kinetin)	Virginia	16.33 cd	81.67 cd	8.667 c-e	Creamy	Compact	Moderate
	CC Bengal	14.67 e-g	73.33 e-g	9.667 bc	Yellow	Friable	Moderate
	Jati	10.33 h	51.67 h	8.667 c-e	Creamy	Friable	Poor
	Motihari	15.00 d-f	75.00 d-f	8.333 de	Creamy	Compact	Moderate
	Kobi	8.667 ij	43.33 ij	10.00 b	Creamy	Friable	Poor
T ₄ (2 mg/liter BAP)	Virginia	20.00 a	100.0 a	8.333 de	Creamy	Compact	Plenty
	CC Bengal	19.33 a	96.67 a	9.000 b-e	Creamy	Compact	Plenty
	Jati	16.00 c-e	80.00 c-e	8.333 de	Creamy	Compact	Moderate
	Motihari	7.000 k	35.00 k	10.00 b	Light green	Friable	Poor
	Kobi	14.67 e-g	73.33 e-g	10.00 b	Yellow	Losse	Moderate
T ₅ (1 mg/liter BAP)	Virginia	17.33 bc	86.67 bc	8.667 c-e	Light green	Compact	Plenty
	CC Bengal	14.33 fg	71.67 fg	9.667 bc	Creamy	Compact	Moderate
	Jati	14.33 fg	71.67 fg	8.667 c-e	Yellow	Friable	Moderate
	Motihari	10.00 hi	50.00 hi	11.33 a	Yellow	Friable	Poor
	Kobi	13.33 g	66.67 g	10.00b	Creamy	Loose	Poor

Note: Mean values having common letters are statistically identical at 5% level of significance as per DMRT

From the above results it may concluded that T₄ (MS +2 mg/liter BAP +0.5 mg/liter IAA) with Virginia, and all the genotypes performed well in T₂ (MS +2 mg/liter kinetin +0.5 mg/liter IAA) regarding different callus characters.

to latter stage. Calli were mostly creamy to greenish in color and medium in size and showed mostly moderate in abundance. They were mostly friable, hard, dry or sometimes moist.

Analysis of variance for total no. of explants showing callus, % callus induction, days required for callus initiation showed significant mean sum of square both variety treatment and their interaction (Table 1).

Out of five different treatments presented in the Table 2, Virginia and CC Bengal performed the best (100% and 96.67% respectively) callus induction ability in T₄ treatment followed by Jati(80%), Kobi(73.33%) and Motihari (35%) (Fig.1). T₂ also showed better result. Virginia under this treatment gave 93.33% callusing followed by CC Bengal, Motihari, Jati and Kobi (80%, 78.33%, 73.33% and 36.67%, respectively). Virginia gave satisfactory callusing 86.67% under T₅ treatment followed by CC Bengal and Jati (71.67% of each). Virginia and Motihari gave 81.67% and 75% callusing respectively under T₃ treatment and proved itself the poor one in

respect of callusing than other three treatments of various phytohormonal combinations.

Kinetin and BAP, both the cytokinin has a wide range of use in tobacco callus induction and both have a true potentiality. In the present investigation, the true reflections of the above statement have been proved. But the average callusing, percentage of BAP was more satisfactory than kinetin in the study. The mean performance of BAP was 77% callusing followed by kinetin 72.33% callusing under the same level of combination of hormonal concentration (Table 2).

Out of five genotypes, Virginia ranked first for callus induction (100%) in T₄ treatment and 93.33%, 86.67% and 81.67% callusing under T₂, T₅ and T₃ treatment respectively. On the contrary, Motihari and Kobi gave comparatively poor callusing against all the treatments (Table 1). From the above findings, we may conclude that hormone free MS medium have no potentiality to produce callus. Higher doses of kinetin and BAP are proportional to higher callusing. Genotypes have showed a profound influence under different

concentrations and combinations of treatments. The variation in callus induction ability among the test materials might be due to genotypic difference. Similar results were reported by Venkateswarlu *et al.* (1989), Amante (1996) and Ali *et al.* (2007).

Organogenesis via callus

Shoot proliferation of five *Nicotiana* genotypes showed a distinct range of variation against each and every concentrations and combinations of phytohormones. Percents of shoot regeneration were different in different treatment and also different in genotypes. Among the genotypes, the highest shoot regeneration (100%) was found in Virginia under T₂ and T₄ treatment and best callusing was found (100%) under T₄ treatment. Against all the treatments, Virginia showed the best performance than rest of the genotypes.

The results for shoot regeneration on days required for shoot initiation, total number of callus with shoots and percentage of shoot regeneration are presented in Table 10. All the parameters are statistically significant

and showed variations among the interactions. In case of total number of callus with shoot, best interaction was found in Virginia with T₂ (20.00) and T₄ (20.00) followed by CC Bengal with T₂ (19.67). T₂ and T₄ have marked themselves for number of callus with shoots. Considering the parameter, percentage of shoot regeneration, Virginia also performed superior result (100%) with T₂ and T₄. Rakleviciene and Sauliene (2001) also found better somatic embryogenesis with Benzyl Aminopurine (BA).

Virginia exhibited better performance against all the treatments than the rest of the genotypes in the present study. Kobi with T₁ treatment required maximum days to shoot initiation. From the above discussion it may be concluded that Virginia is the best genotype which exhibit superior shoot regeneration potentiality for all characters followed by CC Bengal (Figure 2). Guo *et al.* (2004) also found varietal differences on shoot regeneration using different hormonal treatments.

Table 3. Effects of different concentrations of hormone in MS medium on shoot regeration from leaf derived calli of *Nicotiana* species

Traetments	Variety	Total number of calli with shoot	% Shoot regeneration	Days required for shoot initiation
T ₁ (without hormone)	Virginia	14.00 h	70.00 g	10.00 d
	CC Bengal	12.00 jk	60.00 ij	11.67 c
	Jati	15.00 fg	75.00 ef	10.33 d
	Motihari	8.333 n	41.67 m	13.00 b
	Kobi	8.000 n	40.00 m	15.33 a
T ₂ (2 mg/liter kinetin)	Virginia	20.00 a	100.0 a	6.000 j
	CC Bengal	19.67 a	98.33 a	8.000 fg
	Jati	17.00 d	85.00 c	8.000 fg
	Motihari	16.00 e	80.00 d	6.333 ij
	Kobi	16.33 e	81.67 d	12.00 c
T ₃ (1 mg/liter kinetin)	Virginia	18.67 b	93.33 b	7.000 h
	CC Bengal	15.33 f	76.67 e	8.333 f
	Jati	15.00 fg	75.00 ef	8.333 f
	Motihari	17.33 cd	86.67 c	6.000 j
	Kobi	11.33 lm	56.67 kl	10.00 d
T ₄ (2 mg/liter BAP)	Virginia	20.00 a	100.0 a	5.000 k
	CC Bengal	18.33 b	91.67 b	6.000 j
	Jati	17.67 c	86.67 c	6.667 hi
	Motihari	13.33 i	66.67 h	10.00 d
	Kobi	11.00 m	55.00 l	12.67 b
T ₅ (1 mg/liter BAP)	Virginia	17.00 d	85.00 c	6.000 j
	CC Bengal	14.67 g	73.33 f	7.000 h
	Jati	13.67 hi	68.33 gh	7.667 g
	Motihari	12.33 j	61.67 i	9.000 e
	Kobi	11.67 kl	58.33 jk	10.00 d

Note: Mean values having common letters are statistically identical at 5% level of significance as per DMRT

Initiation of roots

For the better survival of regenerated shoots, developed from the explants, root initiation and development is necessary. Without root, regenerated plant may survive in artificial culture media but if we want to grow them on soil, it is essential to have proper root (Figure 3) of every regenerated plantlet to grow and survive in ground. Although various rooting media are used *in vitro* culture, but in present study three types of rooting media were used for root initiation. Their individual effect has been illustrated in Table 4.

Capacity of root initiation varied in a wide range due to difference in hormonal concentrations and combinations as well as difference of genotypes. The highest performance of root initiation was shown by Virginia (90%) with hormone free $\frac{1}{2}$ MS (T₁) and full MS (T₃) media followed by CC Bengal (90%) with T₃ and 80% with T₁ treatment. Motihari scored 80% under T₁ and T₃ treatment while Jati performed 80% in the treatment T₃ and 70% under T₁ treatment. Kobi gave the lowest result among the genotypes all the three treatments. Although all the above-mentioned rooting materials have a good report to initiate root but in the present investigation, hormone free full MS gave excellent result than other. MS-supplement with 0.5 mg/liter IBA performed worst results. This finding is dissimilar to Zhang *et al.*, (1998) reported that the best plant growth regulators for root induction is IBA but similar to Ali *et al.*, (2007) observed that the roots developed well on hormone free MS media in tobacco cultivars.

Plantlet establishment

After proper root development, small plantlets were

fit to transfer to ground or pots. All the agar extracts washed off properly. This washing was done with running tap water. High care was taken so that no roots got damaged. The soil, to which the plantlets would be transplanted (soil: sand: cow dung = 1: 2: 1) should be placed in a small pot, plantlets forced on this soil gently, it demanded proper amount of watering by Hogland's solution.

Table 5. Comparative survivability of regenerates of five genotypes of *Nicotiana sp.*

Planting condition	Name of the genotypes	Number of plants transplanted	Number of plants survived	Survival rate (%)
In pot	Virginia	10	8	80
	CC Bengal	10	8	80
	Jati	8	5	62.5
	Motihari	8	6	75
	Kobi	6	4	66.67

When new leaves started to initiate, the plantlets were then ready to consume normal water. In the pot, Virginia and CC Bengal showed better survivability (80%) followed by Motihari (75%), Kobi (66.67%) and Jati (62.5%) (Table 5). The survived plants then gave vigorous growth with proper leaf development (Fig. 4).

In this experiment, *in vitro* regeneration potentiality of five *Nicotiana* genotypes has been observed by using leaf discs as explant. Virginia was found superior genotype in terms of callus induction, somatic embryogenesis and plantlet establishment followed by CC Bengal variety. Since genetic engineering

Table 4. Effect of hormone free $\frac{1}{2}$ MS, full MS medium and MS supplemented with 0.5 mg/liter IBA on root induction of five *Nicotiana* genotypes (using 10 shoots)

Treatments	Varieties/ Genotypes	Total number of shoot with root	Percent root formation	Days to root initiation
T ₁ (Hormone free $\frac{1}{2}$ MS)	Virginia	9	90	16
	CC Bengal	8	80	18
	Jati	7	70	20
	Motihari	8	80	16
	Kobi	6	60	21
T ₂ +0.5 mg/liter IBA	Virginia	8	80	20
	CC Bengal	7	70	21
	Jati	6	60	22
	Motihari	5	50	20
	Kobi	3	30	21
T ₃ (Hormone free full MS)	Virginia	9	90	15
	CC Bengal	9	90	16
	Jati	8	80	14
	Motihari	8	80	12
	Kobi	7	70	18

Fig. 1 Development of callus from the genotype of Virginia using MS + 2 mg/liter BAP+ 0.5 mg/liter IAA, 2) Initiation of shoot from the callus of CC Bengal genotype using MS + 2 mg/liter kinetin + 0.5 mg/liter IAA, 3) Root initiation from regenerated shoot of Virginia in full MS medium and 4) Survived plant after hardening of Virginia derived from leaf explant.

developed the efficient methods for the regeneration of viable shoots from cultured tissues, this protocol can be followed for genetic manipulation for improvement of *Nicotiana* genotypes.

References

- Afifi S I, Borollosy A M and Mahamoud S Y M. 2007. Tobacco callus culture as a propagating medium for cucumber mosaic cucumovirus. *Int. J. Virol.*; Dept. Agril. Microl., Fac. Agric. Ain Shams Univ., Cairo, Egypt; 3(2): 73-79.
- Alam S M, Iqbal M T, Amin M S and Gaffar M A. 1989. Narcotic crops: Environmental requirements of tobacco, production and development of agronomic crops, *first edn.*; P.79.
- Ali G, Hadi F, Javier M and Khan M A. 2007. Callus induction and *in vitro* complete plant regeneration of different cultivars of tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum* L.) on media of different hormonal concentrations. Dept. Biotech., Univ. Malakand, Pakistan; 6(4): 561-566.
- Amante A D, Zamora A B and Javier E L. 1996. Response of *Nicotiana tabacum* and F₁ hybrids to anther culture. *Philippine J. Crop Sci.*; 1(11): 21.
- BBS, 2006. Statistical Yearbook of Bangladesh. Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics. Planning Division, Ministry of Planning, Govt. Peop. Repub. Bangladesh, Dhaka; P. 144.
- Blakeslec A F, Belling J, Franham M E and Berger A D. 1992. A haploid mutant in the jimson weed, *Datura stramonium*. *Science*; 55: 646-647.
- Guo W, Bai Y, Lai Z, Chen X and Li T. 2004. Plant regeneration in *Nicotiana tabacum* through somatic embryogenesis. *J. Fujian Agric. Foret. Univ. Natural Sci.*; 33(30): 369-372.
- Murashige T and Skoog F. 1962. A revised medium for rapid growth and bioassay with tobacco tissue culture. *Plant Physiol.*; 15: 473-497.
- Rakleviciene D and Sauliene I. 2001. Morphogenic competence of tobacco and asparagus *in vitro*, related to phytohormonal treatment and lighting conditions. *Inst. Bot., Lithuania*; 55(5/6): 225-230.
- Venkateswarlu T, Subhashini U and Anjiani K. 1989. Anther culture studies in White Burley tobacco. *Tobacco Res.*; 15(2): 120-122.
- Zhang Z Q, Zhou Y, Zhong W J, Zhang J J and Yin L Q. 1998. Induction of adventitious buds and regeneration plants from cotyledons of Chinese cabbage (*Brassica campestris* L. spp.). *Acta Agric. Shanghai.*; 14(2): 25-28.